

Linear Regression with Keras: A Practical Approach

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Abstract

Regression analysis is a statistical method used to estimate the relationships between variables that exhibit cause-and-effect relationships. The primary focus of univariate regression is to analyze the relationship between a dependent variable and a single independent variable, formulating a linear equation that describes this relationship. In this paper we presents a practical approach to implementing a linear regression model using Keras, a high-level neural networks API built on TensorFlow.

Keywords: Linear regression, Keras, Tensorflow

INTRODUCTION

Linear regression is one of the simplest and most widely used techniques in statistical modeling and machine learning. It is employed to predict the value of a dependent variable based on one or more independent variables, establishing a linear relationship between them. Despite its simplicity, linear regression serves as the foundation for many complex modeling techniques and is applicable across various fields, including finance, healthcare, and social sciences.

There are two main types of linear regression: Simple Linear Regression and Multiple Linear Regression. In this paper we use Simple Linear Regression. This is

the simplest form of linear regression, and it involves only one independent variable and one dependent variable. The equation for simple linear regression is:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X \quad (1)$$

where:

Y is the dependent variable

X is the independent variable

β_0 is the intercept

β_1 is the slope

Keras, a powerful and user-friendly API for building neural networks, offers an efficient way to implement linear regression models. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive guide to creating a linear regression model using Keras, focusing on its practical aspects. We will cover data generation, model creation, training, and evaluation, making the concepts accessible to both beginners and experienced practitioners.

METHODOLOGY

Data Generation

In this paper, we will explore the Boston Housing dataset, which includes data collected by the U.S. Census Bureau regarding housing conditions in Boston, MA. The dataset features 14 distinct attributes, one of which represents the median value (in thousands of dollars) of homes in various suburbs. We will use this dataset to demonstrate how to build a predictive model that estimates the median home price based on a single attribute: the average number of rooms in a house. Keras offers the `load_data()` function to easily access this dataset. Typically, datasets are divided into training and testing components, and the `load_data()` function returns a tuple corresponding to each. Each tuple includes a 2-dimensional array of features (e.g., `X_train`) and a vector containing the associated target values for each sample (e.g., `y_train`). In this setup, the rows of `X_train` represent the different samples in the dataset, while the columns correspond to the various features. For the purpose of this demonstration, we will focus solely on the training data to illustrate how to train a model. However, it is crucial in practice to utilize the test data to evaluate how well the trained model

performs on unseen data. Here we plot the median price of a home vs. the single feature ('Average Number of Rooms').

Figure 1: Median price of a home vs. the single feature ('Average Number of Rooms').

Understanding Neural Networks: Key Concepts and Terminology

The diagram below illustrates how this model can be represented as a neural network with a single neuron. We will use this straightforward example to introduce essential components and terminology of neural networks. The input data x consists of a single feature, specifically the average number of rooms, while the predicted output y' is a scalar value representing the predicted median price of a home. Each data sample in the dataset corresponds to the statistics for a suburb in Boston.

The model parameters, denoted as m and b , are learned iteratively throughout the training process. As you may know, these parameters can be calculated using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method in a closed form. Alternatively, we can solve this problem iteratively through a numerical technique known as Gradient Descent, which serves as the foundation for training neural networks. While we will not delve into the specifics of gradient descent here, it is crucial to recognize that it is an iterative method utilized to optimize the model parameters.

Figure 2: The network contains just a single neuron that takes a single input (x) and produces a single output (y'), which is the predicted (average) price of a home.

The single neuron has two trainable parameters, which are the slope (m) and y-intercept (b) of the linear model. These parameters are more generally known as weight and bias, respectively. The single neuron has two trainable parameters, which are the slope (m) and y-intercept (b) of the linear model. These parameters are more generally known as weight and bias, respectively. In this example, you can think of the neuron as the mathematical computation of $\omega x + b$, which produces the predicted value y' .

Neural Network Parameter Adjustment

The diagram below illustrates how model parameters (w and b) are updated throughout the training process. Initially, these parameters are set to small random values. As training data is fed into the network, the model's predicted output (y') is compared to the actual ground truth (y) for each sample in the dataset. This comparison yields a loss value, which serves as feedback for adjusting the model parameters to enhance prediction accuracy.

The weight update process consists of two key steps: Gradient Descent and Backpropagation. While the intricate mathematical details of these algorithms are not crucial at this stage, it is essential to recognize that training the model involves an iterative process aimed at refining the parameters.

Figure 3 : Neural Network Weight Update

The Loss Function we use can take many forms. In this case, we will use Mean Squared Error (MSE) which is a very common loss function used in regression problems.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - y'_i)^2 = mean(SSE)$$

The fundamental goal is to minimize the value of this function, which represents the error between our model and the training dataset. In the equation above, m denotes the number of training samples.

RESULT

The network diagram presented earlier illustrates the most basic form of a neural network. This network consists of a single layer with one neuron, which produces an output of $wx+b$. For each training sample, the predicted output y' is compared to the true value from the training data, allowing us to calculate the loss. This loss value is then utilized to adjust and refine the model parameters. All of the details associated with training a neural network are taken care of by Keras, as summarized in the following workflow:

- Build/Define a network model using predefined layers in Keras.
- Compile the model with `model.compile()`
- Train the model with `model.fit()`
- Predict the output `model.predict()`

We trained our model for 18 epochs, with the results from the final epoch shown below.

18/18 [=====] - 0s 5ms/step - loss: 69.9668 - val_loss: 101.7632

Figure 4: Visualizing Training Results

The loss curves displayed above are quite typical for model training. Notice that there are two distinct curves: one representing the training loss and the other representing the validation loss. Initially, both losses are high but steadily decrease over time, eventually leveling off with little to no further improvement after approximately 30 epochs. As the model is trained solely on the training data, it is expected that the training loss remains lower than the validation loss.

Make Predictions using the Model

We can now use the `predict()` method in Keras to make a single prediction. We pass a list of values to the model (representing the average number of rooms), and the model returns the predicted value for the price of a home for each input. For the average number of rooms given by $x=[3,4,5,6,7]$, we will predict the corresponding house prices

Predicted price of a home with 3 rooms: \$9.7K

Predicted price of a home with 4 rooms: \$12.4K

Predicted price of a home with 5 rooms: \$15.1K

Predicted price of a home with 6 rooms: \$17.8K

Predicted price of a home with 7 rooms: \$20.5K

Figure 5: Visualizing the our Model and Data

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we explored linear regression within the framework of a simple neural network. We demonstrated how to utilize Keras to model and train the network, enabling it to learn the parameters of the linear model. Additionally, we covered techniques for visualizing the model's predictions.

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